

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Political Leprosy and Godfatherism: How Media Shape Party Loyalty and Political Survival in Nigeria

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Abstract

The research paper "Political Leprosy and Godfatherism: How Media Shapes Party Loyalty and Political Survival in Nigeria" examines the pervasive influence of godfatherism in Nigerian politics, where democratic principles are selfishly circumvented to benefit political buccaneers. It also highlighted how political elites and financiers dominate electoral processes and governance, hence, trivialising party supremacy and promoting personal interests over the public good. Godfatherism as a significant issue in Nigeria's politics, highlighting its negative impact on democracy and the imposition of political leaders by powerful elites, also forms the focus of this paper. The study analysed the role of media in shaping political narratives and party loyalty, focusing on media framing strategies. The findings emphasised the necessity for political leaders to prioritise fairness, transparency, equity, equal rights, and the welfare of the people to enhance good governance. The study anchored its theoretical framework on agenda-setting theory and the Selectorate theory of the media on shaping party loyalty and political survival in Nigeria. The study concluded that political leprosy and godfatherism are creations of the media. The media's exertive influence on giving prominence to salient issues ignites hyperreality and diversionary perception among the audience, thereby promoting a politically convoluted polity. This study, therefore, recommended that for true democratic representation and sustainable political survival of Nigeria's democracy, party loyalty should reflect fairness, equity, and equal rights, being the bedrock of maintaining consistency and sustainable political culture.

Keywords: Political leprosy, godfatherism, loyalty, political survival, media

1. Introduction

The landscape of Nigeria's political system has been, over the years, infiltrated by various shades of politically influenced interests that conflict with democratic and representative interests. Self-driven political actors have successfully created around themselves a formidable aura of vested interest, continually perpetuating themselves in the guise of power, where their self-significant ego is largely protected by the envy of their followers rather than expanding their political clout through better performance and stewardship for their followers. The fear of political leprosy among the political actors in Nigeria's political space is overwhelmingly quaking the democratic bedrock of Nigeria, as betrayal, mistrust, political backstabbing, reneging on promises, inconsistencies, and political party maneuverings remain abnormally normal in the system.

The origin of the word 'Leprosy' dates back to Greek and Latin (Lendrum, 1952). The disease is associated with rejection, isolation, ostracism, social segregation, stigmatisation, and impairments. Thus,

political leprosy can be described as a situation whereby a political actor or politician is systematically and politically alienated, ostracised, and disassociated from being functionally relevant in a political party as a result of some suspicious manifest and latent political impairment such as corruption, mistrust, disloyalty, and/or anti-party activities engagement. Therefore, this political behaviour or practice can be described as deadly to democratic principles as leprosy.

It is worth noting that political leprosy results from a failed fellowship with the political godfathers. Political godfatherism has long been a defining feature of Nigeria's political landscape, where influential figures dictate the political fate of candidates and parties. These power brokers use their financial resources, networks, and influence to install protégés in key political positions, often prioritising personal interests over democratic values (Olorunmola, 2017). This system fosters a form of political dependency that limits the autonomy of elected officials and weakens democratic institutions. Over time, this practice has evolved into what can be termed "political leprosy" - a condition in which politicians who defy godfathers face political isolation, character assassination, and electoral disadvantages.

In Nigeria, politics is sometimes seen not as politics but as "Politricks," where the dos and don'ts of democracy are strictly adhered to in perfect reverse. According to Ibrahim (2003), godfathers are 'men who have the power personally to determine who gets nominated and who wins [an election] in a state'. According to Chimaroke Nnamani (as cited in Albert, 2005), a godfather is simply a self-seeking individual out there to use the government for his own purposes. Godfatherism is characterised by influential political figures who manipulate electoral processes and control political outcomes, undermining democratic principles and fostering political instability.

The role of media in this dynamic is crucial, as they shape public perception, party loyalty, and political survival. Traditional media historically served as platforms for shaping political narratives, while digital and social media have introduced new dynamics of engagement (Omoera, 2020). The media frames and determines who is politically leprous and who should gain the exit card into the political leprosarium once such a politician has a fallout with his political gathering or godfather.

2. Statement of the Problem

Political godfatherism has remained a major impediment to Nigeria's democratic development, influencing electoral outcomes, governance structures, and party politics using the media as a very ready tool for conveying its democratically injurious influence. Politicians who refuse to align with and 'conditionally' cling to their godfathers often suffer political leprosy, exile, and negative framing. This study seeks to examine how the media shape party loyalty and political survival in the context of godfatherism and political leprosy in Nigeria.

3. Theoretical Framework

The study anchors on two complementary theoretical foundations:

Agenda-Setting Theory

This theory posits that mass media possess the capacity to influence the salience of issues in public discourse. By consistently highlighting specific topics, the media effectively signal their importance to the audience, thereby shaping public perception (McCombs & Shaw, 1972). In Nigeria, media can amplify certain political narratives or downplay others, thereby influencing party loyalty.

Selectorate Theory

Introduced in 2003 by De Mesquita et al., the theory posits that the survival of political leaders depends on the size of their "selectorate" and "winning coalition." In systems where a small coalition—often comprised of political godfathers—holds sway, leaders prioritise the interests of this select group to ensure retention.

4. Conceptual Review

4.1. Concept of Political Leprosy and Godfatherism

'Political leprosy' is metaphorically used to describe the systemic alienation of political actors who defy the established political hierarchy. Godfatherism involves influential figures (godfathers) who exert control over political aspirants (godsons), ensuring their electoral success in exchange for loyalty (Ikelegbe, 2014).

4.2. Media Influence and Digital Revolution

Social media platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and WhatsApp have emerged as powerful tools for countering traditional media narratives controlled by political elites (Omoera, 2021). These platforms have facilitated political activism and alternative discourse, challenging the hegemony of political godfathers.

5. Methodology

For this study, a library research method was employed, involving a systematic and comprehensive review of existing literature. This method, also known as desk research, involves gathering data from existing sources such as academic journals, books, and online resources (Asemah & Nwaoboli, 2024).

6. Consequences of Godfatherism and Media's Role

The emergence of godfatherism poses a great threat not only to good governance but also to socio-economic development. Electorates are often denied the privilege of electing people of their choice. Godfatherism in Nigeria is often predatory, where the primary motive is wealth acquisition from government coffers.

Media coverage of political conflicts, such as the feud between Chief Nyesome Wike and Siminalaye Fubura (2023-2025), demonstrates how political affiliations shape citizens' perception. Media framing can either support or challenge the narratives promoted by godfathers, impacting political survival and legitimacy (Ojebuyi & Ekennia, 2013).

7. Discussion

The prevalence of godfatherism has led to a decline in genuine political mentorship. Instead of nurturing leaders based on merit, the focus shifts to maintaining control. This manipulation erodes public trust in the electoral system. Political leprosy and godfatherism are paired political vernacular used to undermine democratic tenets. The most recent instance is the ongoing political crisis in Rivers State, which led to a declaration of a State of Emergency on March 18, 2025.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

8.1. Conclusion

This study concludes that political leprosy and godfatherism are significantly influenced by media portrayal. The media's exertive influence promotes hyperreality and diversionary perception among the audience.

8.2. Recommendations

1. **Promote Merit-Based Leadership:** For sustainable political survival, party loyalty should reflect fairness and equity rather than godfatherism.
2. **Media Accountability:** The media should adopt an objective stance and resist partisan pressures to act as a counterbalance to godfatherism.
3. **Institutional Reforms:** Reforms targeting transparency and accountability are necessary to promote democratic values and mitigate political instability.

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